

NORMAL AND PATHOLOGICAL PHYSIOLOGY

MANAGEMENT OF MEDICAL ABORTION IN HOME AND OUTPATIENT SETTINGS, AN OVERVIEW

Zhekov Zh.

*MU Varna, Department Obstetrics and gynecology
Specialized Hospital of Obstetrics and gynecology, Varna*

Abstract

An attempt has been made to systematize the knowledge about the possibilities of conducting medical abortion at home and the need to follow it in outpatient conditions.

A documentary retrospective method is used - a review of the scientific database for the last 10 years.

Medical abortion is the preferred method of administration for women who have an unplanned or unwanted pregnancy. This is a solution in countries where surgical abortion is prohibited. In outpatient conditions, the preferred procedure is surgical abortion - it takes little time, can be performed at any time, but often there are complications. Medical abortion takes longer, is associated with pain symptoms and discomfort, low cost of medical service. Depending on different conditions, the management and choice of a particular method is determined by the patient's preferences and the ability to perform the specific service. Through telemedicine, the time to receive the service is shorter by approximately 4.0 days. Lower education, younger age, and pregnancy after 20 weeks are significantly associated with a preference for face-to-face communication and medicated abortion in stationary conditions.

Medicated abortion in Ambulatory conditions has a future in modern obstetric-gynecological practice. With a very good Administrative Organization of women's Health, provided by the appropriate qualified medical staff, together with clear information provided to the woman - allows her to manage the Medical abortion properly and safely in outpatient conditions. This model of care has been proven safe, effective and acceptable for clients and improves access to early abortion. For Bulgaria, this practice has yet to be popularized and administratively organized.

Keywords: abortion, choice of method, Mifepristone and Misoprostol, Telemedicine.

Introduction:

Abortion is the most common gynecological procedure - over 56 million per year worldwide [3, 7], with only 10.0% to 15% of all abortions occurring in the second trimester [4]. Worldwide, there is a trend of expanding medicated abortion (MA) indications during the Apostille trimester, incl. in outpatient conditions. There is no established protocol for the safe termination of pregnancy during the Ambulatory trimester. As the main method of providing this service is accepted the use of telemedicine. In a modern sense, the concept of telemedicine has existed since 1924. when it appeared in the United States in a radio news article, with a picture on the cover of a doctor examining a patient and sending his results over the radio. The first demonstration was made in 1951 at The New York World's fair. It is believed that the term telemedicine was introduced into the medical literature in 1974. with the publication of R. G. Mark (Telemedicine system: the missing link between homes and hospital Mod.Nurs.Home-1974y, N 32) [5]. Management of carrying out an abortion procedure requires a definition of the term of pregnancy, the possibilities for carrying out a certain method - at home or in outpatient conditions, pain management [8,9].

According to other sources, it was first recorded in 1970. he used the term in the publication [11]. Telemedicine is a way of providing health services in which providers (consultants) and clients are separated by distance [13]. This interaction can take place in real time (synchronously), e.g. by phone or video. But it can also occur asynchronously when a request is sent and the

answer is provided later, e.g. by e-mail or text / voice / audio message [13,15].

Telemedicine counseling allows women to do Medical abortion (depending on the stage of pregnancy) in their own home with remote support from the abortion provider. They do not need personal contact with the provider. There is no need to visit the abortion clinic before then, unless there is a reason for doing so: uncertain date of Apostille, Apostille - last Menstrual cycle; risk of ectopic pregnancy; complex medical conditions.

Telemedicine is gaining popularity as a service for the provision of Medical abortion and in many countries legally organized practices for its application are sought. The use of telemedicine as part of the abortion service also has historical precedent. Women in Northern Ireland used telemedicine for early and outside legal circumstances and outside the health system for almost a decade before its use was legislated.

The Medical abortion tablets were provided by members of feminist websites who provided them with detailed information on how to use them and what effects to expect from women. A number of more recent studies have found that many of their experiences are similar to those managed through England's National Health Service (NHS) [12].

The aim of this review is to conduct a comparative analysis of medical abortion in inpatient and outpatient settings during the Apostille trimester of pregnancy: in terms of effectiveness, early and late complications, using the electronic resources of information in the last 10 years.

Results

Medical abortion in outpatient conditions-effectiveness and complications: 10-12 g.w.: A systematic review of nine prospective comparative cohort studies involving 4,522 women up to 56 days (8 g.w.) from pregnancy, it was shown that the incidence of full abortions and the incidence of unwanted complications were the same for the use of both at home and in the medical establishment [6]. A non-randomized comparative study involving 731 rural and urban women from India up to 63 days pregnant (9 g.w.) [6] and 10 weeks of pregnancy [6] found no difference in abortion success or adverse complications. In the United Kingdom during the COVID-19 pandemic 52,142 women up to 70 days (10 g.w.) pregnancy used at home as the rates of complete abortions are over 98.0% and the incidence of serious complications is less than 1.0% [6].

Abortion results from 64-84 days' amenorrhea (9-12 g.w.) were published in a study from 2011 in terminations of pregnancy up to 70 days' amenorrhea with 200 Mifepristone followed by 24-36 hours later Misoprostol at home at a dose of 800 µg - 97.7% efficacy was found. The effectiveness of a similar abortion scheme has been investigated in other studies [1]. In a study in 2012. 729 pregnancy interruptions were analyzed over a period of 64-70 days' amenorrhea compared to a period of 57-63 days (the same dosage was used with Mifepristone 200 mg and Misoprostol 800 µg buccally). The effectiveness was the same in both groups: in the group 57-63 days (8-9 g.w.) - 93.5% (95% CI 90-96); in the group 64-70 days (9-10 g.w.) - 92.8% (95% CI - 89-95). The number of ongoing pregnancies also does not differ significantly (57-63 days - 3.1%; 95% extravehicular - 1.6-5.8; 64-70 days - 3.0%; 95% extravehicular - 1.5-5.7). High technology acceptability and patient satisfaction were high in both groups, as follows - 87.4% and 88.3%. The authors conclude that medical abortion with Mifepristone and Misoprostol in outpatient practice is an effective and acceptable method of Terminating Pregnancy up to 64 - 70 days of amenorrhea (9-10 g.w.). The safety and effectiveness of Misoprostol, admitted at home and in outpatient conditions was also established in a meta-analysis involving 9 prospective cohort studies and covering n = 4522 abortions [2]. Serious complications were not reported when taken at home, and the conclusion was that there was no difference in effectiveness, according to the place of taking the drug – home or outpatient conditions.

Medical abortion in outpatient conditions and telemedicine: This model of Home Care has been proven safe, effective and acceptable to clients and improves access to abortion [10]. From a systematic review involving four randomized control studies comparing telemedicine with Medical abortion services and in-person clinics, it was found that there was no difference between the two groups in rates of successful abortions or continued pregnancies. Satisfaction with telemedicine services is high and comparable to normal clinical abortion services [13].

A study in the United States in 2011. comparing women who received Medical abortion through telemedicine or face-to-face at doctor visits concluded that

providing the service through telemedicine is an effective method and has high levels of patient acceptability. Data were obtained for 223 telemedicine patients and 226 face-to-face patients-99.0% of telemedicine patients and 97.0% of face-to-face patients had a successful abortion; 91.0% of all patients were very satisfied with their abortion, but telemedicine patients were more likely to recommend the service to a friend; 25.0% of telemedicine patients would prefer face-to-face communication.

Two prospective cohort studies reporting on the effectiveness of telemedicine for the delivery of Medical abortion during the COVID-19 pandemic used reported LMP of women alone to determine gestational age and eligibility for medical abortion [6]. One study from England compared a cohort of 22,158 women who received a traditional Medical abortion before a pandemic, which included a personal assessment and routine ultrasound, to a group of women who received a Medical abortion with telemedicine (if they had a low risk of ectopic pregnancy and their self-reported Apostille was consistent with a gestational age of less than 10 weeks (n =18435) or a traditional Ma if they did not meet these criteria (n =11549) [6].

Treatment success, serious adverse reactions, and ectopic pregnancy rates did not differ between the two cohorts. 11 women (0.04%) of the telemedicine cohort were found to have gestational age greater than the expected 10 weeks. All were able to complete their abortions at home without incident.

Another, smaller Scottish cohort study followed a similar telemedicine protocol, but included women who were up to 12 g.w. by self-assessment of the LMP [6].

Of the 663 women included in the cohort, at 79.0%, gestational age was determined only with the LMP. Due to uncertain gestational age, ultrasound was made at 14.0%, and to confirm intrauterine pregnancy at 5.0%. Complete abortion occurred in 98.0% of cases, with continued pregnancy occurring in less than 1.0% of women. In 2.4% of women, additional medical services were sought, but no serious adverse complications were reported. Although they can usually remember their aposematic when asked to determine their gestational age or eligibility for MA based on the aposematic, a small fraction of women's estimates differ from those of their abortion providers.

Three studies compared the determination of gestational age made with the help of the LMP with those determined by a provider assessment [6]. All three studies also assessed the ability of women to determine for themselves whether they were eligible for Medical abortion based on their LMP. In the earliest of these studies, 10.0% of the 173 women in India who used a worksheet and their LMP to determine their gestational age determined that they were eligible for Medical abortion, while providers determined that their pregnancy was above the 56 - day limit (8 g.w.).

In Nepal, 13.0% of the 3,091 women who used their LMP and modified gestational dating wheel to determine their eligibility for Medical abortion using a 63-day limit (9 g.w.), were incorrect compared to supplier estimates. Finally, in Ghana, 770 women used a

modified gestation wheel to determine whether their pregnancy was before or after 13 g.w. Compared to the provider's assessment, 3.6% of women incorrectly determined that their pregnancy was less than 13 g.w. Of these women, one pregnancy was 13 g.w. (0.1% of 770), 15 were 14 g.w. (1.9%), seven were 16 g.w. (0.9%), 2 were 18 and 22 g.w. (0.3% each), and 1 was 28 g.w. (0.1%).

Discussion: telemedicine accelerates access to early abortion. It enables more clinics to provide abortion services, facilitates the use of Medical abortion among women living in remote areas, reduces clinic waiting times [12]. In a UK study of over 50,000 cases, telemedicine found that the time to receive the service was shorter by approximately 4.2 days [12]. Also, telemedicine may reduce abortion-related costs such as absence from work and travel costs. Lower education, younger age, and pregnancy after 20 g.w. were significantly associated with a preference for face-to-face and steady-state communication [12].

Requirements for conducting Medical abortion in outpatient conditions:

- *Women can take the Misoprostol at the medical facility or at home.*

Two prospective, non-randomized multicenter cohort studies conducted in the United States, which together included 701 women, showed that between one-third and a half of the women who were offered the use of Mifepristone at home or in a clinic chose a Home Application [6]. In similar studies conducted in Azerbaijan [6] the majority of women also chose home use 72.0% and 64.0%, respectively.

- *After 11 g.w. It should only be taken in a medical facility.*

While the safety and effectiveness of the ambulatory use of ambiguities as part of the repeatable and repeatable mode is well established up Misoprostol to 70 days of pregnancy, the upper gestational limit at which Repeatable can be safely used at home is not well established. However, ambiguities, ambiguities are recommended for outpatient use of ambiguities up to 70 days of pregnancy (10 g.w.) the search for optimal doses for abortion in the period 10-13 g.w. continues. Expert clinical advice available 24 h / 7 days a week.

A study [15] found that 13% (n= 224/1726) of women made contact with a clinician for help after taking the Apostille at home for an abortion before 9 weeks' gestation. Most of those who called did not have indications to visit the Emergency Medical Assistance (84.0%, n=188), while a minority (1.0%, n=36) were advised to visit the CSMP for review. Overall, only 2.0% (36/ out of 1,726) of women showed up for an emergency check-up. This study highlights the need for expert clinical advice available 24 h / 7 days a week for women with early Medical abortion at home.

Risks associated with Medical abortion in outpatient conditions:

- *The greatest risk is if Medical abortion is performed in the presence of an unrecognized ectopic pregnancy.*

- *The second major risk is associated with an underestimated gestational age determined at the diagnosis and stage of pregnancy.*

- *The third most important risk is the lack of routine in women to properly assess the severity of clinical symptoms and their combination with symptoms of concomitant systemic diseases.*

Like any new activity related to medical services, telemedicine has its advantages and disadvantages. The *first*-the greatest risk when performing Medical abortion in outpatient conditions is the presence of unrecognized ectopic pregnancy. The *second* logistical problem is the incorrectly determined gestational age-most often underestimated. From 5.0% to 15.0% of women self-identify their gestational age incorrectly! When the true gestational age is in the range of II-nd trimester, and is treated with an abortion methodology used in I-st trimester due to undervalued gestational age - there is a high risk that the abortion will remain incomplete, with retention of abortion parts in the uterus and all related complications threatening the health and life of the woman.

The *third* significant risk associated with the use of Medical abortion in outpatient settings is the occurrence of very rare severe complications of abortion such as uterine rupture, profuse bleeding, ascending infection and allergic reaction or intra-vascular coagulation (DIC). Any delay in recognizing and diagnosing these complications is associated with a risk to the woman's life. On the other hand, Medical abortion in outpatient conditions and the use of telemedicine for its management is an excellent alternative in conditions of pandemic, living in an area with geographical remoteness or lack of health personnel to ensure the performance of legal abortion.

In Bulgaria at this stage there is no established and legally regulated practice for the use of Medical abortion in outpatient conditions, but with the development of telemedicine standards - such is forthcoming. Telemedicine reduces the time frame for abortion and reduces the costs associated with it. That is why currently there is a legislative, administrative and health-medical regulation of the use of telemedicine, so that it becomes an effective and safe part of the procedure of Medical abortion and in Bulgaria.

Conclusions

The management of the choice and conduct of a given method of abortion requires a precise medical decision and economic cost - benefit. It is necessary to proceed from the individual assessment of each case. to clarify the medical and social implications. to prevent the pain symptom and psychosocial consequences of the decision to abortion.

There is currently no comparative data for home use of misoprostol after 11 g.w. It is accepted that abortion regimens that involve taking additional doses of Misoprostol are not suitable for abortion in outpatient conditions. The WHO suggests that when women have access to a source of accurate information and a healthcare provider, they can manage the abortion process themselves by the age of 12 g.w.

In 12g.w. or more with a medical abortion is usually performed in a medical facility. However, there is no evidence showing that medical abortion outside the medical establishment is unsafe. If necessary, consultative activities with different specialists are planned.

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